

RADxUP

RADx-UP Publications Summative Content Analysis Report

Insights from Publications in Scholarly Journals

December 2024

Executive Summary

Purpose and Overview of Methods

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team uses content analysis to examine outcomes, impacts, and lessons learned from RADx-UP peer-reviewed publications describing their COVID-19 testing and vaccination research. Using a codebook T&E developed for the analysis, independent reviewers individually coded assigned published peer-reviewed publications for study characteristics, translational science benefits, and thematic categories of impact.

This report presents content analysis findings from **334** publications pulled between September 22, 2021 and June 30, 2024 via PubMed and Scopus databases and RADx-UP Project surveys.

Figure 1. Phases of RADx-UP publication content analysis.

Publication Characteristics

Populations served. Hispanic or Latino populations ($n = 84$ publications), children and adolescents ($n = 64$), and Black and/or African American populations ($n = 63$) were the three most frequently identified underserved priority populations across RADx-UP publications (Figure 2). Publications more frequently pertained to the experiences of urban populations ($n = 66$) compared to rural populations ($n = 34$). Schools were the most frequently reported research setting ($n = 62$) by publication authors, followed by residential care facilities ($n = 22$), community health centers ($n = 22$), in-home ($n = 12$), hospitals ($n = 11$), and prisons or jails ($n = 7$).

Publication methods. Publication authors most frequently reported observational study designs ($n = 169$), with quasi-experimental ($n = 43$), experimental ($n = 23$), and simulation ($n = 3$) designs being employed less frequently. Most publications employed quantitative analysis ($n = 195$), followed in frequency by qualitative analysis ($n = 52$), mixed-methods ($n = 43$), editorial ($n = 18$), literature review ($n = 13$), and clinical case studies ($n = 4$).

A majority (60%) of publications reported at least one community engagement strategy in project activities regarding recruitment, planning, implementation, or dissemination.

Translational Science Benefits Model Impacts

T&E adapted the four domains (clinical, community and public health, policy, and economic) and associated indicators (**Appendix A**) of the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) by [Luke et al. \(2018\)](#) to code articles with translational benefits with respect to COVID-19 testing and vaccination. RADx-UP publication authors reported the community and public health benefits of both testing and vaccination most frequently, compared to the other translational science benefits domains. The three most-reported

Most Frequently-Identified Underserved Populations

Figure 2. Number of RADx-UP publications ($N = 334$) about the three most-reported underserved populations. Note: A publication can be coded with multiple underserved populations.

Most Frequently-Cited TSBM Benefits Associated with COVID-19 Testing

Figure 3. Number of RADx-UP publications ($N = 334$) with the three most-reported testing benefits from the Translational Science Benefits Model.

indicators of community and public health benefits of testing included testing accessibility ($n = 72$), delivery and uptake of tests ($n = 60$), and community testing services ($n = 59$; Figure 3). Publications indicated projects directly increased access to testing or services that offer tests (e.g., [Hendricks et al., 2023](#); [Whanger et al., 2022](#)) or improved understanding of factors that contribute to improving testing acceptability (e.g., [Marsiglia et al., 2024](#); [Searcy et al., 2023](#)).

For vaccination benefits, understanding vaccine hesitancy was most frequently reported ($n = 73$), followed by delivery and uptake ($n = 50$), then vaccination accessibility ($n = 38$; Figure 4). Publication authors indicated that projects increased vaccination delivery and uptake by addressing the availability and/or distribution of vaccines to underserved communities to promote increased vaccine uptake (e.g., [Mohareb et al., 2024](#); [Bigelow et al., 2022a](#)).

Nine publications included reflections on actual or potential impacts of COVID-19 testing and vaccination policies, with particular emphasis being placed on the role of policy in protecting the health of workers (e.g., [Lee et al., 2022](#); [Syme et al., 2022](#)) and school-aged children (e.g., [Vestal et al., 2023](#); [Kelly et al., 2022](#)).

Thematic Categories of Impact

Publications were most frequently categorized as exploring the impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement ($n = 79$) or the social and behavioral factors influencing the access and uptake of vaccination ($n = 81$) and/or testing ($n = 73$). The following sections (A-D) detail additional findings.

A. Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Factors Related to Testing and Vaccination

Thirty-one publications noted disparities in testing and vaccination hesitancy, motivation, access, and uptake among diverse underserved populations. Initiatives like in-reach and outreach through clinics, mobile units, reduced-cost/free testing and vaccination, employer-sponsored resources, and at-home testing improved access and uptake to COVID-19 testing and vaccination.

Most Frequently-Cited Benefits from TSBM Indicators Adapted for RADx-UP

Figure 4. Number of RADx-UP publications ($N = 334$) with the three most-reported vaccination benefits from the Translational Science Benefits Model.

- **Sociodemographic factors.** Race, ethnicity, sex, gender, age, education, employment, socioeconomic status, presence of comorbidities, political affiliation, access to health care, and having been vaccinated against COVID-19 are associated with testing uptake. Black and/or African American, Hispanic or Latino, Asian American, Native Hawaiian, and Pacific Islander populations tend to show greater vaccination hesitancy compared to other racial/ethnic groups. Other individual-level factors, including attitudes, beliefs, motivation, and behaviors, have also been identified as facilitators or barriers to testing uptake and vaccine hesitancy and/or uptake ([Bray et al., 2024](#); [Mast et al., 2023](#); [Buro et al., 2022](#)).
- **Interpersonal and social factors.** Misinformation is identified as a factor that increases testing and vaccination hesitancy. Trusted messengers, especially people within social networks and healthcare providers, are crucial in addressing hesitancy and improving uptake.
- **Environmental, community, and other socio-political factors.** Vulnerable populations may face disparities in testing and vaccination access based on social determinants (e.g., transportation and language barriers). Facilitators at the community, organizational, and governmental levels can improve access, acceptance, and uptake, including in-school testing, syringe exchange programs, and state-run free testing sites.

Participants described everyday social contacts, family, friends, and members of their community as providing critical motivation for becoming vaccinated.

– [Moore et al., 2023](#)

B. Structural Barriers to Testing and Vaccination

Authors of **41** publications reported structural barriers to testing. These barriers include transportation or driving times, location of centers or services, inflexible work schedules, fear of losing employment while getting tested, wait times or scheduling, fear of exposure while waiting to be tested, and the cost of testing (e.g., [Martin et al., 2024a](#); [Whanger et al., 2022](#); [Chamie et al., 2022](#)). [Berkley-Patton et al., 2024](#) designed a COVID-19 testing trial at African American churches; the program aimed to provide free testing during church and ministry activities while providing other outreach services to reduce barriers of time required to access testing and financial barriers.

Twenty-two publications observed or evaluated interventions against at least one structural barrier to COVID-19 vaccination; many barriers to vaccination paralleled aforementioned testing barriers. Frequently-reported barriers to vaccination include

inconvenience of and/or lack of transportation to vaccination locations (e.g., [McClure et al., 2024](#)), unfulfillment of basic needs (e.g., [Valasek et al., 2022](#); [Martin et al., 2024b](#)), and linguistic barriers (e.g., [Marsiglia et al., 2024](#), [Martinez et al., 2022](#)).

C. Impact of Community Engagement and Collaborative Partnerships

Sixty out of the **79** publications coded under 'impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement' described these impacts in detail within the following areas:

- **Utilize multi-sector partnerships to implement, adapt, and promote testing/vaccination.** Multi-sector partnerships involving academic partners, community-based organizations, and health departments were developed or leveraged to implement, improve, and adapt research activities to community needs. These partnerships effectively promoted testing and vaccination uptake within underserved communities. Multi-sector partnerships were used to address vaccine hesitancy, adapt intervention strategies to community needs, and reduce infection transmission within schools ([Purvis et al., 2024](#), [Goldman et al., 2023](#); [Gillard et al., 2022](#)).
- **Strengthen recruitment and data collection.** Twelve publications described in detail how their community partnerships helped them identify and recruit eligible participants. Some studies specifically used targeted strategies such as recruiting from existing studies ([Strathdee et al., 2023a](#)) or engaging community health workers ([Barrett et al., 2022](#)), community-based organizations ([Xu et al., 2024](#); [Berkley-Patton et al., 2024](#); [Wang et al., 2023](#); [Barrett et al., 2022](#); [Rodriguez et al., 2022](#)), or trained faith leaders ([Berkley-Patton et al., 2022](#)) to achieve enrollment targets.
- **Improve community capacity for research and community workforce development.** Five publications described how they partnered with community-based organizations to improve community capacity for research by hiring and training trusted members already living within communities to implement research activities ([Begay et al., 2024](#); [Marzan-Rodríguez, 2023](#)).
- **Inform health messaging, outreach, and dissemination strategies.** Twenty-six publications described how community partnerships, trusted leaders, and local networks were used to disseminate culturally appropriate messages and other relevant information within communities. Feedback from these partners ensured culturally appropriate messaging, while investments in social marketing campaigns and multiple dissemination channels promoted testing and vaccination ([Berkley-Patton et al., 2024](#); [Meekers et al., 2024](#); [Dillard et al., 2022](#)).
- **Use community advisory boards and community-based participatory research to guide research implementation.** Eighteen publications employed a community-based participatory approach and developed community-based testing strategies (e.g., [D'Agostino et al., 2024](#); [Haroz et al., 2022](#)). Additionally, ten publications established or utilized community

advisory boards (CABs) to provide guidance on culturally appropriate study materials, address community priorities, discuss testing barriers and facilitators, and provide feedback on outreach strategies (e.g., [Bateman et al., 2024](#); [Strathdee et al., 2023a](#)).

- **Build sustainable trusted relationships within communities.** Ten publications emphasized the importance of building trusted partnerships by engaging partners with relevant lived experience or language skills, while another publication highlighted the role of serving as a COVID-19 information resource in establishing trust within underserved communities ([McClure et al. 2024](#); [Budd et al., 2022](#)).
- **Evaluate the impacts and strengths of community engagement.** Twelve publications evaluated community engagement strategies. For example, [Barrett et al. \(2022\)](#) highlighted the effectiveness of partnerships with community-based organizations in recruiting and retaining Black and Latino residents. [Stadnick et al. \(2022a\)](#) estimated the time commitment differences across phases of community engagement activities, showing that more time is spent during project startup and recruitment compared to the maintenance phase, and assessing CAB member engagement satisfaction and activities associated with a co-designed COVID-19 testing program in San Diego. [Maras et al. \(2024\)](#) evaluated community partnerships and identified two key results: 1) trust and relationship as foundational pieces of community engagement; 2) importance of implementing and adapting community-informed research strategies.

D. Lessons Learned from Implementation and Intervention Strategies

Intervention Implementation Successes

- **Community-driven partnerships and collaborations.** Positive outcomes in RADx-UP projects are attributed to robust community-academic partnerships (e.g., [Strathdee et al., 2023](#)), which enhanced research capacity and improving research design skills (e.g., [Ko et al., 2022](#)). Stakeholder involvement in intervention development resulted in more community-relevant findings and bidirectional learning (e.g., [Garibay et al., 2024](#)). Sustainable outcomes from community partnerships include community members becoming investigators and systemic changes,

The community partners stressed the benefits of honoring and creating a bilingual space. This theme highlights the importance of having a community and academic partner open to collaboration and can dedicate the staff, time, and financial resources to conducting bilingual activities.

– [Garibay et al., 2024](#)

such as integrating youth entrepreneurship education into high school curriculums ([Ko et al., 2022](#)).

- **Culturally tailored outreach and intervention strategies.** Tailored intervention strategies, including engaging trusted peers and culturally specific outreach, improved vaccination and testing accessibility and uptake (e.g., [Compton et al., 2024](#); [Garibay et al., 2024](#); [Dillard et al., 2022](#)). Peer-led intervention sessions significantly increased testing rates and culturally tailored approaches resulted in higher testing numbers among specific communities (e.g., [Bazzi et al., 2023](#); [Strathdee et al., 2023a](#)). Multiple media and outreach strategies, such as flyers, radio announcements, and social media, were effective in promoting interventions and recruiting participants ([Budd et al., 2022](#)).
- **Evidence-based intervention design and implementation approaches.** Publications described interventions grounded in evidence-based behavioral and implementation science theories (e.g., [Bazzi et al., 2023](#); [Strathdee et al., 2023a](#)), addressing knowledge gaps and attitudinal barriers. Community-based participatory research principles guided intervention design, implementation, and community outreach, allowing flexibility and cultural tailoring (e.g., [Begay et al., 2024](#); [Dillard et al., 2022](#)). Adaptive approaches were used to optimize interventions based on ongoing feedback (e.g., [Windsor et al., 2022](#)).

Intervention Implementation Challenges

- **Community-academic partnership and engagement challenges.** Community-engaged research is acknowledged as transactional, demanding significant time, dedication, and patience. Challenges include difficulties in maintaining and strengthening community partnerships beyond the study duration and administrative obstacles, such as institutional review board (IRB) delays, affecting partner relationships.
- **Resource limitations.** RADx-UP publications highlighted resource limitations, such as time demands, funding constraints, and staffing shortages, for community-engaged research. Fast-paced project timelines, staff shortages, and regulatory hurdles affected intervention implementation and vaccination uptake.
- **Limitations of study implementation design.** Complexities of implementing randomized controlled trials in real-world settings are evident, with challenges such as ethical concerns, objections to randomization, and the need for responsiveness to establish trust. Implementing study design activities that rely on virtual communication channels may have introduced selection bias and excluded community members without internet access. Also, self-reporting for vaccine uptake behaviors could have introduced reporting bias.
- **Sampling, selection bias, and methodological limitations.** Despite multiple engagement strategies, publications identified trade-offs and limitations of sample size and representativeness. Specifically, a small sample size may limit the

ability to detect significant changes and recruiting from a specific target population may restrict the applicability of findings to the broader population or underrepresented groups.

Implications and Recommendations for Future Research

- **Need for rigorous studies.** RADx-UP projects emphasize the need for more rigorous comparative, longitudinal, and experimental studies to understand barriers and facilitators to successful implementation.
- **Prioritizing funding and addressing health disparities.** Future research should prioritize funding for community-engaged interventions beyond COVID-19 testing and vaccination to address health disparities in underserved populations.
- **Adaptability and flexibility in research.** Continuous adaptation of interventions, especially in response to SARS-CoV-2 variants and community priorities, is crucial for future research. Adopting flexible study designs aligned with community values and ethical considerations are emphasized for impactful health equity research interventions.
- **Building sustainable community-research partnerships.** Sustained community engagement is essential, and establishing mechanisms for ongoing feedback from community partners ensures interventions remain relevant and effective over time.